

Product- and Business Development of StratiFlex™

M. Spanggaard

DTU Civil Engineering & DTU Engineering Management, Technical University of Denmark

Building and maintaining thermal stratification in hot water storage tanks offer great energy- and cost saving potentials, e.g.:

- Solar thermal heating systems; end users can save up to 25 % in auxiliary energy
- Electrical heated water tanks; end users can save up to 50 % in energy cost

Potentials which are insignificantly released today due to lack of proper technology.

An innovative and efficient stratification technology was invented at DTU in 2005. Several research projects have attempted to develop the technology into a marketable product. An accelerated long term durability test late 2013 put an end to the expectations. The technology will never be applicable to systems enclosing lime containing water.

The aim of this present project is to:

- Invent a new highly efficient and durable stratification technology
- Develop the technology into a commercially attractive product
- Plan and startup a business based on selling the new stratification device

December 2013 a groundbreaking new technology was invented, offering superior stratification, potentially becoming the most cost-efficient stratification device on the market!

Figure 1 Prototype of StratiFlex™

A long term durability test equivalent to more than 10 years of operation has demonstrated a continuous high efficiency despite massive expose to lime sediments. The component materials are PTFE and stainless steel making the product exceedingly resistant to aging. The current prototype called the StratiFlex™ has a higher efficiency than any other product on the market. The product is scalable as well as adaptable to any size and type of system.

The company EyeCular Technologies has been registered, an ELFORSK project granted and an investment from CAPNOVA May 2014 has secured the next years of growth. A 0-series production is estimated late 2014 and global market launch anticipated spring 2015 at the "ISH" fair in Frankfurt together with our most likely first customer, TWL-Technologie.

For further information please visit www.eyecular.com.